

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE TEACHER'S IMAGE IN ORGANIZING DIDACTIC PROCESSES FOR MILITARY EDUCATION STUDENTS

Nazarov Tohir Toshpulatovich

**Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute Associate Professor of the Special
Training Cycle of the Faculty of Military Education.**

Telephone: 945407400

Email address: nazarovtohir910@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The image of a military education teacher represents a harmonious combination of his professional skills, moral qualities, appearance and reputation before the team. Especially for officer-teachers working in the educational system of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the image is closely related to high discipline, responsibility and dedication. An image is not formed by chance, but is developed gradually, based on a clear plan and a systematic approach. This process encompasses personal development, professional training, and social relationships.

Enter. In the current era, no matter how deep knowledge, vast experience a creative teacher has, no matter how well he or she masters educational methodologies and technologies, he or she is required to have sufficient respect, authority, and attractiveness in the eyes of his or her students, colleagues, and the public. From this point of view, it is appropriate to talk about image, about the teacher having his or her own image. Image is a concept about a person that has a number of meanings, and is a manifestation of the form and style of behavior, as well as the symbolic appearance of the subject in the process of entering into relationships[1]. Today, image is a simple information product that reflects a person's self-expression, speech and appearance, taking into account conservative or creative views. In the process of relations and communication with the public and between people, the concept of "Image" acquires a special meaning and content. According to various sources, the need to create an image was formed in the activities of economists engaged in entrepreneurial activities, and thus in the 60s of the 20th century, the American economist Baldwin introduced the word "Image" into circulation, proving that it is a useful tool for achieving success in business.

The purpose of the study. Each specialist conducts research in his field, direction, based on the object of research, his purpose. The lack of boundaries in obtaining information, the breadth of the flow of information are also changing the psyche of people, their relationships, the form of communication and methods of influence. In order to influence young people, it is becoming increasingly important, first of all, to gain a place in their hearts. Image design begins with clarifying goals based on personal vision and values[2]. People who are currently respected: know what they want and work hard to achieve their goals; clearly express their desires and goals when communicating with others; "create" themselves,

respecting the personalities and individuality of their colleagues, and achieving success through their own merits and efforts.

Methods of organizing research. For those in the teaching profession, who are involved in public relations or interpersonal interactions, image is directly linked to one of the most important components of success, and it has become an important condition for the effective performance of professional duties.

Professional image can be managed and directed according to changing personal and professional goals.

Management is carried out in three stages:

- designing the desired image, taking into account the personal goals and characteristics of the image audience;
- to realize the desired image in work and life;
- receive feedback, analyze and further develop the image.

It is important to remember that the image is not only of an individual, but also of a team. Each team, large or small, has its own reputation, influence, and social opinion about itself. For example, within an educational institution, there are military faculties that are recognized with greater respect and trust by the pedagogical team, or an educational institution that is especially noteworthy among educational institutions.

Research results and discussion. The “initial image” of a military educator is one of the most important factors in his professional activity. This image is formed at the first meeting and leaves a lasting impression in the minds of listeners (students). The initial image is manifested through the appearance, speech culture, behavior and professional competence of the educator. Therefore, the assessment of his success should be based on systematic and clear criteria. Several key indicators are taken into account when assessing the success of the initial image. In particular, the teacher's adherence to discipline, clear and fluent speech, the ability to establish effective communication with the audience, and self-confidence are of great importance[3]. Also, his/her adaptation to the military environment, his/her commanding and explanatory style are also considered as evaluation criteria. These aspects determine the overall impression of the teacher.

Observation, questionnaire and analysis methods can be used in the evaluation process. For example, by studying the opinions of students, it is determined how the teacher is perceived. In addition, observations conducted by management or experienced specialists also provide important information. Based on the results, strengths and weaknesses are identified, which serve as the basis for further development. If shortcomings are identified in the initial image, it is necessary to take specific measures to correct them. For example, it is recommended to work on speech, strengthen psychological preparation, pay attention to appearance or participate in training to improve pedagogical skills. Also, self-analysis and regular feedback can help improve the image[4]. According to experts, the image arises in the lower layers of the human psyche. That is why it is convenient for people to perceive and occupies an important place in their minds. When we talk about the image as a specific psychological concept, it is manifested in the form of a social instruction, a symbol that is a tradition.

Summary. In conclusion, the image of a military educator directly affects his professional success. By correctly assessing it and making the necessary adjustments, the educator can organize his activities more effectively. This will have a positive impact not only on his personal development, but also on improving the quality of military education..

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